

THE CHALLENGES OF “INCLUSIVE EDUCATION” IN PROFESSIONAL TECHNICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

School inclusion is a delicate and complex process of high importance for a society that needs to develop coexistence strategies that consider the wonderful diversity of its citizens. The inclusive policy, currently, is based on the action of the Libras interpreter, as most teachers are not qualified to welcome this clientele. The research that originated this article sought to identify the difficulties of inclusion of the deaf student in the Vocational Technical Education of the Federal Institute of Piauí - IFPI from the analysis of the social representations of servers and students on the subject. Forty-five (45) questionnaires were applied to identify social representations regarding the inclusion of deaf students on campus, generating 72 (seventy-two) evocations. The analysis was based on the theory of the Collective Subject Discourse and used DSCsoft2.0 (Tolteca). Inclusion is linked to equality - it was the strongest evocation. Listeners and non-hearers are in fragile territory in the construction of an effective communication process, and the Libras interpreter is the interface between these two worlds, with an urgent need to improve their working conditions, considering programs for the prevention of occupational diseases and expansion of the framework of these professionals. For teachers, Inclusion needs to be linked to a “dignified education” that creates opportunities for the development and autonomy of students, and that gives them the opportunity to enter the job market. This requires serious planning, adequate training and investments in improving educational instruments and environments.

Key Words: Inclusive education, Vocational education, social representations.

INTRODUCTION

The research aimed to identify the difficulties for the implementation of the Inclusion Policy of the Federal Institute of Piauí - IFPI. The theory of social representations was the reference for the analysis of the conceptions of professors, servants and students regarding the theme “Inclusion of the disabled student”.

The focus of the research focused on the Inclusion of the deaf person in the Technical Education of the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Piauí - IFPI, on the Teresina Zona Sul campus - CATZS. The main instrument of the research was the

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application of questionnaires with the academic community and the accomplishment of structured interviews with representatives of the Pedagogy and Teaching sectors of CATZS. The research fits into the exploratory, descriptive study modality, within a qualitative approach, taking the survey and treatment of quantitative data in a complementary perspective. The qualitative approach is best suited for the analysis of social representations, where the subjective character of the elements involved is preponderant.

The work was developed with the collaboration of the team from the Center for Assistance to People with Specific Needs - NAPNE, responsible for the intermediation between teachers and students. After the analysis, important elements were identified for the improvement of Inclusion in the teaching-learning process of the Occupational Safety discipline, generating subsidies for other disciplines. Contributions to the improvement of institutional inclusive policy were also listed.

Characterization of the Intervention Scenario

The IFPI - Teresina Zona Sul campus, chosen for the research, has about 1,200 students, 100 professors and 70 employees and is part of a national teaching network that brings together different teaching modalities covering high school technical courses in integrated, concomitant and subsequent to high school; and higher courses, in the form of Technological Course and Licentiate.

According to data reported by the Support Nucleus for People with Special Needs - NAPNE, during the research period, the campus received 16 students with a demand for Inclusion care. The list of students with specific needs in 2018 (2nd semester) are: 09 Deafness; 01 Dyslexia; 01 Autistic Spectrum Disorder/Asperger's Syndrome; 01 Visual Impairment; 01 Attention Deficit; 01 Physical Disability/Deformity of the Right Lower Limb; 01 Microcephaly, Low Vision, Malformation in Hands and Feet, Learning Difficulty; 01 Physical Disability, Scoliosis. Of the disabled students enrolled at the time of the research, about 50% were deaf and asked for help from interpreters in Libras to be able to attend classes.

These numbers have increased in a non-linear proportion, since the campus began to receive students with disabilities, which demonstrates the growing interest of the deaf community that now feels empowered and visualizes concrete possibilities of insertion in the job market. The institution has also carried out a publicity campaign about its Inclusion

policy, which has reached and attracted more and more young people and adults with disabilities.

In Brazil, numerous documents and guidelines have made reference to the educational and social rights of people with specific educational needs, based on international documents such as the Salamanca Declaration (UNESCO, 1994).

Inclusive Education, according to Sasaki (1997, p. 41), can be conceptualized as a “process by which society adapts to be able to include in its general social systems people with special needs and, simultaneously, they prepare to assume their roles. in society. [...]”.

It was understood that the research needed to identify and evaluate the role and importance of all agents involved in the educational inclusion system. From the observation of the experiences lived in the IFPI-Teresina Zona Sul campus and, considering the elements involved in the teaching-learning process and in the reception of the disabled student in society, the scheme presented in Figure 1 is proposed.

Figure 1: Elements involved in the process of educational inclusion in the IFPI
Source: Prepared by the author (2019)

THEORETICAL REFERENCE

The Collective Discourse - Analysis of Social Representations

The social psychologist Serge Moscovici, author of reference, defines social representations as “a particular type of knowledge having the function of elaborating behaviors and communication between individuals” (MOSCOVICI, 2012, p. 27). Analyzing the structure of this form of expression of “social thinking”, one can understand a social

representation as a set of knowledge elements linked to a social object and the constituent elements of each representation are basic units called cognems (ROUQUETTE, 1994 apud WACHELKE, 2014).

The theory traditionally most adopted for the analysis of Social Representations is the 'core theory'. This theory explains that social representations have elements that form a central nucleus that define and organize them. This core is complemented by a peripheral system that contains conditional and flexible elements related to practical aspects, presenting eventual contradictions, as well as idiosyncrasies. Thus, it is understood that to characterize social representations, and the processes associated with them, it is necessary to know the elements of the representation structure, that is, it is necessary to characterize the basic structural properties of the main ideas and beliefs about the social object in question. focus (MOLINER, 1994 apud WACHELKE, 2014).

The elaboration of the questionnaires followed the proposal of Wachelke (2014) – the Qualiquic. Qualiquic consists of six open-ended questions. For each of them, research participants are invited to provide two answers, focusing on two different aspects of the social object. Respondents were instructed to write a sentence for each aspect. According to the author of the technique, it is not an association procedure nor a task elaborating elaborate discursive production (WACHELKE, 2014). Data analysis was performed with the help of Tolteca's DSC Software 2.0, developed by Fernando Lefèvre and Ana Maria C. Lefèvre. For the analysis of the social representation of a given object, the frequency of appearance of an element and the degree of importance attributed to it were considered.

PROJECT EXECUTION METHODOLOGY

Research Characterization

The research is part of an exploratory, descriptive study modality, within a qualitative approach, taking the survey and treatment of quantitative data in a complementary perspective. The qualitative approach is better suited to the analysis of social representations, where the subjective character of the elements involved is preponderant.

In order to make the project viable, the team was formed by a research professor, who teaches the Occupational Safety discipline, a servant of the Support Center for the Person with

Specific Needs - NAPNE and 05 deaf students, voluntary scholarship holders who attended this discipline.

In the investigation of the contents of the social representations, the technique of word associations was used, which is the basis for the Collective Subject Discourse – CSD. To this end, the qualitative technique – Qualiquic – was adopted, with adaptations, which is easy and simple to apply, and has the advantage of bringing together representational contents characterized by their relations with the object of representation, based on a simplified list of descriptive connectors, practical and evaluative aspects of the base cognitive schema model, based on Walchelke's (2014) proposal.

The following instruments were adopted for data collection: the application of questionnaires, the photographic record and the report of experiences/case study of the Occupational Safety Discipline. The research was also based on a documental analysis of the specific literature and institutional documents that deal with the Inclusion Policy.

Conducting Interviews and Application of Questionnaires

As criteria for the selection of the sample, the following were taken into account: the heterogeneity of the sample with regard to gender, age and time of teaching practice, according to the guidelines of Couto (2008 apud ARRUDA, 2002), but also the function and importance of activities performed by the person in relation to the research object.

In collecting data from the professors, a questionnaire was applied to a sample of 07 professors from the professors' staff, 09 servers, being 05 representatives of the Support sectors (General Management, Financial Management, NAPNE, Pedagogy and Social Assistance), 23 are students listeners and 06 are deaf students of the Building Technician, Nutrition and Dietetics Technician and Kitchen Technician courses. To collect data from these students, it was necessary to mediate an interpreter specialized in Brazilian Sign Language. In total, 45 questionnaires were applied to identify the social representations related to the question “What is Inclusion”, which generated 72 evocations.

The results were processed and transformed into tables and infographics using Excel and DSCsoft software. The analysis of the interviews sought to identify convergences and divergences for the design of the social representations of the agents involved, based on the theory of the Collective Subject Discourse.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Categories for the Concept of “School Inclusion” and Groupings of Responses Based on Key Expressions and Associated Ideas

The questionnaires for teachers, servers and students had two questions: “In your opinion, what is the “Inclusion of the Disabled Person in the Technical Education of the IFPI?” In your opinion, what factors interfere with the inclusion of the Disabled Person in the IFPI Technical Education?” Nine categories of representations were identified, considering the association of the ideas expressed by the interviewees. Below is a table with the characterization of each category.

Table 1 shows the categories and the frequency of evocations grouped in the categories according to the groups of interviewees, in a comparative way.

Category	deaf students	listening students	professors	servers	support sector
A – Equality	58,3%	14,3%	0,0%	28,6%	34,2%
B – Diversity and respect	0,0%	14,3%	0,0%	0,0%	2,6%
C – Adequacy and qualification	33,3%	8,6%	45,5%	28,6%	31,6%
D – Everyone's Right to Education	0,0%	31,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
E – Qualification for entering the job Market	0,0%	2,9%	18,2%	0,0%	5,3%
F – Inclusion is socialization	0,0%	14,3%	18,2%	28,6%	13,2%
G – Inclusion is welcome	8,3%	5,7%	0,0%	0,0%	5,3%
H – Inclusion is worthy teaching	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	2,6%
I – Inclusion is promoting autonomy	0,0%	8,6%	0,0%	14,3%	0,0%

Table 1: Frequency of evocations grouped in categories according to the groups of respondents
Source: Prepared by the author (2019)

Adopting the technique of “identifying (illuminating)” the key expressions, it was possible to organize the interviewees' ideas into groups or categories.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Analyzing the Social Representations of the Respondents, in relation to what is 'Inclusion in IFPI Technical Education'

a) Listening students

The evocations of this group focused mainly on the following categories: Equality (14.3%), Right to Education (31.4%), Adequacy and Qualification (14.3%); Inclusion is Socialization (14.3%).

The speech of hearing students argues that students - deaf and hearing - must be considered on equal terms, which means that both have, without distinction, the right to Education, and that both have the capacity to succeed in studies to obtain a training professional. Thus, it is up to educational institutions to “accept diversity as an inherent fact of society”, and it is their (the institution's) responsibility to “adapt to the needs” of their students, whatever their characteristics. One of the answers clearly demonstrates these conclusions when it defines that Inclusion is “appreciation of human diversity”, the “diverse transformations in the school environment” being natural.

However, a part of the interviewees argues that the Institution needs to “support the disabled person” in order to “replace them in society so that they can have the same rights as social and thinking individuals”. Another answer says that Inclusion “is being empathetic, respecting and trying to help in some way”. These expressions call attention to the dimension “coexistence and socialization”. Thus, Inclusion would only be effective in so-called 'normal' schools, where there is coexistence with diversity.

b) Deaf students

The evocations of deaf students were concentrated in only 03 categories: Equality (58.33%), Adequacy and Qualification (33.33%), and Reception (8.33%).

The speech of deaf students can be well exemplified in the testimonies that define Inclusion as “receiving the person without discrimination and making the person feel included”, and “having no difference, everyone is equal, that's how it needs to be”. For these students, it is up to the Institution to offer “equal opportunity for all” and “qualified education for the deaf”. It is necessary to “seek resources for the person with disabilities to learn” and “Teachers willing to teach the disabled”.

Egalitarian treatment, without prejudice, is the central idea that stands out in the evocations of deaf students who declare that everything must start from this attitude of welcoming with respect and without prejudice.

c) Students

This was the only group that did not have evocations in the Equality category. However, it presented expressions that configured interesting categories. The categories related to the responses of this group are: Adequacy and Qualification (45.45%); Qualification for Insertion in the Labor Market (18.18%); Inclusion is Socialization (18.18%); Inclusion is Promoting Autonomy (9.09%); and Inclusion is Reception (9.09%).

This group, as was to be expected, focused its evocations around observations on the quality of education to be offered. As representatives of the group responsible for the mediation of knowledge, and aware of their role in the success of the teaching-learning process, the teachers draw attention to the aspects that interfere in the technical training of the future professional.

A statement that exemplifies this situation well is that which says that Inclusion is “an opportunity for the disabled person to achieve technical-professional training” and that it represents setting up “a new school, with the capacity to receive and teach the disabled person with dignity”. In this evocation, and in other expressions, the professors declare that it is not enough to bring the student to Technical Education, without ensuring conditions for them to have adequate training, and the market can trust the graduate professional. A statement that stands out says: “The IFPI is putting the disabled in school, but the disabled are not receiving due attention. It's not just putting the disabled inside the school, it's making them participate in the school”. Another draws attention to the different expectations of the social sectors: Inclusion for the student is “*“an opportunity for growth, based on the knowledge acquired in the classroom”*”, he “*comes to understand himself as a protagonist of his growth”*”; but for society Inclusion is “*a gain in quality, as a qualified workforce only improves the lives of those involved”*”.

It is noticed that the evocations of the professors, contrary to what one might think, are loaded with valuable reflections because they look at the process as a whole: the professors declare that Inclusion must “*to ensure material and human resources and adequate didactic-pedagogical methodology for teaching the disabled”* which translates into “*adequate infrastructure with accessibility”* and “*professionals trained to meet the needs of the disabled person”*”.

d) Servers

The servers had their evocations gathered with the same proportion of 28.57% in the categories Equality, Adequacy and Qualification and Inclusion is Socialization. To a lesser extent, the category Inclusion is to promote Autonomy was also identified for the group (14.29%).

For civil servants, Inclusion is “allowing people, once without opportunities, to finally complete high school in a dignified way, have a profession and also the possibility of continuing education”, a very representative evocation. In addition, for civil servants Inclusion is “integrating the disabled person into society, showing that they are capable of having a normal life equal to that of everyone around them”.

Inclusion has not yet been fully achieved in the IFPI due to lack of material and structural conditions and this needs to be solved, because, according to an evocation, inclusion is *“to overcome barriers and cross borders”, and thus “have an education system with an adequate structure in every way to receive all individuals regardless of psychological, physical, social conditions”*.

e) Representatives of the Support Sectors

The questionnaire for the employees of the Support Sectors had other questions, but contemplated an equivalent questioning about what School Inclusion would be.

For this group, Inclusion is: *to welcome all people into the education system, regardless of ethnicity, race, gender, sexual orientation, social class and physical, psychological conditions [...]*. One interviewee stated that Inclusion, in his opinion, *“is a set of actions that aim to welcome students with specific needs [...]”* and another stated that *“Social inclusion is welcoming all people at school [...] respecting and providing conditions for their learning and development, as they have the same capacity as the others (students)”*.

Analyzing the Social Representations of the Respondents, in Relation to the Factors That Influence the 'Inclusion in IFPI Technical Education'

The responses of all respondents were grouped into the following categories:

- adequate resources (human and financial resources and adequate structure/accessibility): 37.88%

- respect, awareness and empathy: 24.24%
- institutional policy/have more vacancies: 4.55%
- training of teachers and servers (appropriate methodology and knowledge in Libras): 24.24%
- information and guidance for the deaf: 4.55%
- integration with the family: 4.55%

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The social representations of the teachers indicate a good understanding of the students' needs, and as expected this category is more demanding and critical about the process. Teachers are aware that they need to review their practice, but they do not feel safe to deal with the situation. This gives the impression that “apparently” they have no interest in getting involved. However, many evocations demonstrate that there is a real and deep concern with the problem, although linked to a certain fear of implementing changes, mainly because they are concerned with the technical quality of the training of future professionals, an issue that no other group has raised. Teachers, due to their technical training, are still unable to clearly visualize the mechanisms and alternatives to assist the disabled in all their diversity; one of the reasons for this is that they are aware of the limitations of the system and institutional policies that create regulations and requirements for practice, without providing the necessary resources.

One of the evocations of representatives of other groups states that teachers have to understand that the legislation defines that no student can be left out of the system and that the school is obliged to receive them. However, it was evident that the attitude of teachers must also be proactive, seeking mechanisms to overcome their deficiencies, as they must assume their role as a mediator between deaf students and knowledge at the same level of demand that they do with hearing students.

The praxis in the classroom must be the result of the integration of all these factors, but in the day-to-day reality of public education, the process is reversed: the teacher is the first to be called to initiate Inclusion. In fact, he is the first to face the urgent need to adapt content and methodology, and the maximum responsibility for the student's success or failure has been reserved for him, regardless of the other factors being resolved or not.

It was very clear that for teachers Inclusion must be linked to a "dignified education" that creates opportunities for the development and autonomy of students, and that gives them the opportunity to enter the job market, and, therefore, it must be done with planning and training.

The school needs new equipment and specific materials so that the teacher can overcome the limit of the "apparent" deficiencies of the student who has special characteristics, as well as need to adapt the buildings to the requirements of architectural accessibility. All these factors play a fundamental role so that Inclusion can actually be achieved. The teacher's practice in the classroom must add to all these factors, in an integrated way.

For servers, listening students and representatives of support sectors, the main issue is the reception and socialization of disabled students. For these agents, Inclusion needs to change the reality of the disabled who for decades were left on the margins of society as if they were incapable and did not have the same rights as other people. Equality is the strongest evocation for these agents. Inclusion must also be linked to Equality, Reception, the Right to Education, Socialization, and demands qualification of teachers and servers, as well as the adequacy of the institution.

It is necessary to "look for resources for people with disabilities to learn" and "teachers willing to teach the disabled". Egalitarian treatment, without prejudice, is the central idea that stands out in the evocations of deaf students who declare that everything must start from this attitude of welcoming with respect and without prejudice.

In the interpreters' view, three elements are essential: 1) the implementation of a monitoring program to monitor deaf students; 2) the maintenance of a permanent training program in Libras at the institution; 3) the existence of a team of interpreters to accompany students in extracurricular activities.

There is a need for the institutional policy of Inclusion to address the concern to improve the working conditions of interpreters by maintaining programs to prevent the onset of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMD) and the mental and physical stress caused by their professional activities. This will avoid absences or even dismissals from work due to problems related to repetitive work. In addition, the interpreter team must have enough staff so that it can have the necessary breaks without prejudice to deaf students, that is, there must always be an interpreter in activity, while the other rests.

It is also recommended that this research be disseminated and expanded in view of its exploratory nature given the relevance of the research object.

As can be abstracted from this investigative experience, the challenges are great. But it is precisely on battlefields like this, in Education, that small and valuable victories can be built that will help our students feel more prepared to win their own battles, in more egalitarian and dignified conditions.

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